

Where H is a tensor field of type $(1, 2)$, then

- (b) $H(X, Y) = -A(X)Y$
- (c) $\nabla H(X, Y, Z) = -A(X)g(Y, Z)$
- (d) $\nabla S(X, Y, Z) = \nabla H(X, Y, Z) - \nabla H(Y, X, Z)$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla H(X, Y, Z) &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} g(H(X, Y), Z) \\ \nabla S(X, Y, Z) &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} g(S(X, Y), Z) \end{aligned}$$

Hence

An L-contact manifold will be an L-Sasakian manifold, if

$$(3.4) \quad (B_X \nabla F)(Y, Z) - 2A(X) \nabla F(Y, Z) + A(Y) g(\bar{Z}, \bar{X}) - A(Z) g(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) = 0$$

An L-contact manifold will be a nearly L-Sasakian manifold, if

$$\begin{aligned} (3.5) \quad (a) \quad & (B_X \nabla F)(Y, Z) - 2A(X) \nabla F(Y, Z) + A(Y) g(\bar{Z}, \bar{X}) - A(Z) g(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) \\ &= (B_Y \nabla F)(Z, X) - 2A(Y) \nabla F(Z, X) + A(Z) g(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) - A(X) g(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) \\ &= (B_Z \nabla F)(X, Y) - 2A(Z) \nabla F(X, Y) + A(X) g(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) - A(Y) g(\bar{Z}, \bar{X}) \\ (b) \quad & (B_{\bar{X}} \nabla F)(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) = (B_{\bar{Y}} \nabla F)(\bar{Z}, \bar{X}) = (B_{\bar{Z}} \nabla F)(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}). \end{aligned}$$

This implies

$$(3.6) \quad (B_X \nabla F)(Y, Z) - (B_Y \nabla F)(Z, X) + A(X) g(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) - 2A(X) \nabla F(Y, Z) + A(Y) g(\bar{Z}, \bar{X}) + 2A(Y) \nabla F(Z, X) - 2A(Z) g(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) = 0$$

These equations can be modified as

$$(3.7) \quad (B_X \nabla F)(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) - (B_{\bar{Y}} \nabla F)(Z, X) + 2A(X) g(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) + A(X) \nabla F(Y, Z) + 2A(Z) \nabla F(X, Y) = 0$$

$$(3.8) \quad (B_X \nabla F)(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) - (B_{\bar{Y}} \nabla F)(Z, X) + 2A(X) \nabla F(Y, Z) - A(X) g(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) + 2A(Z) g(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) = 0$$

An L-Contact manifold is called an almost L-Sasakian manifold, if

$$(3.9) \quad (B_X \nabla F)(Y, Z) + (B_Y \nabla F)(Z, X) + (B_Z \nabla F)(X, Y) - 2\{A(X) \nabla F(Y, Z) + A(Y) \nabla F(Z, X) + A(Z) \nabla F(X, Y)\} = 0$$

This gives

$$(3.10) \quad (B_{\bar{X}} \nabla F)(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) + (B_{\bar{Y}} \nabla F)(\bar{Z}, \bar{X}) + (B_{\bar{Z}} \nabla F)(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) = 0$$

An L-Contact manifold is called a generalized L-Co-symplectic manifold, if

$$(3.11) \quad (B_X \nabla F)(Y, Z) + A(Y)(B_X A)(\bar{Z}) - A(Z)(B_X A)(\bar{Y}) - 2A(X) \nabla F(Y, Z) = 0$$

An L-Contact manifold is called a generalized nearly L-Co-symplectic manifold, if

$$\begin{aligned} (3.12) \quad & (B_X \nabla F)(Y, Z) + A(Y)(B_X A)(\bar{Z}) - A(Z)(B_X A)(\bar{Y}) - 2A(X) \nabla F(Y, Z) \\ &= (B_Y \nabla F)(Z, X) + A(Z)(B_Y A)(\bar{X}) - A(X)(B_Y A)(\bar{Z}) - 2A(Y) \nabla F(Z, X) \\ &= (B_Z \nabla F)(X, Y) + A(X)(B_Z A)(\bar{Y}) - A(Y)(B_Z A)(\bar{X}) - 2A(Z) \nabla F(X, Y) \end{aligned}$$

An L-Contact manifold is called a generalized almost L-Co-symplectic manifold, if

$$\begin{aligned} (3.13) \quad (a) \quad & (B_X \nabla F)(Y, Z) + (B_Y \nabla F)(Z, X) + (B_Z \nabla F)(X, Y) - A(X)\{(B_Y A)(\bar{Z}) - (B_Z A)(\bar{Y})\} \\ &- A(Y)\{(B_Z A)(\bar{X}) - (B_X A)(\bar{Z})\} - A(Z)\{(B_X A)(\bar{Y}) - (B_Y A)(\bar{X})\} - \\ &2\{A(X) \nabla F(Y, Z) + A(Y) \nabla F(Z, X) + A(Z) \nabla F(X, Y)\} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

This implies

$$(b) \quad (B_{\bar{X}} \nabla F)(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) + (B_{\bar{Y}} \nabla F)(\bar{Z}, \bar{X}) + (B_{\bar{Z}} \nabla F)(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) = 0$$

Theorem 3.1 A generalized L-Co-symplectic manifold is an L-Sasakian manifold, if

$$(3.14) \quad B_X T = X + \bar{X} + \bar{\bar{X}}$$

Proof. The result directly follows from (3.4) and (3.11).

Theorem 3.2 A nearly L-Sasakian manifold is a generalized nearly L-Co-symplectic manifold, in which

$$(3.15) \quad (a) \quad (B_X A)(\bar{Y}) = g(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) \Leftrightarrow (b) \quad (B_X A)(Y) = -g(X, Y + \bar{Y} + \bar{\bar{Y}}) \Leftrightarrow$$

$$(c) \quad B_X T = X + \bar{X} + \bar{\bar{X}}$$

Proof. Using (3.5) (a) and (3.12), the result follows by simple computation.

Theorem 3.3 A generalized almost L-Co-symplectic manifold is an almost L-Sasakian manifold, if

$$(3.16) \quad (B_X A)(\bar{Y}) = (B_Y A)(\bar{X}) = g(\bar{X}, \bar{Y})$$

Proof. Making the use of (3.9) and (3.13) (a), we get (3.16).

In an L-Contact manifold with the semi-symmetric connection B, Nijenhuis tensor is given by

$$(3.17) \quad N(X, Y, Z) = (B_{\bar{X}}F)(Y, Z) + (B_{\bar{Y}}F)(Z, X) + (B_XF)(Y, \bar{Z}) + (B_YF)(\bar{Z}, X) - 2A(X)g(Y, Z) + 2A(Y)g(Z, X)$$

CURVATURE TENSORS

Let R be the curvature tensor of the connection B and K be the curvature tensor of the connection D, then in an L-Contact manifold, we have

$$(4.1) \quad (a) \quad R(X, Y, Z) = K(X, Y, Z) - (D_X A)(Y)Z + (D_Y A)(X)Z \Leftrightarrow$$

$$(b) \quad R(X, Y, Z) = K(X, Y, Z) - (B_X A)(Y)Z + (B_Y A)(X)Z$$

In an L-Sasakian manifold, we have

$$(4.2) \quad (a) \quad R(X, Y, Z) = K(X, Y, Z) - 2F(X, Y)Z.$$

$$(b) \quad K(X, Y, T) = -A(Y)X + A(X)Y = -S(X, Y) \Leftrightarrow$$

$$(c) \quad K(X, Y, T, Z) = -A(Y)g(Z, X) + A(X)g(Y, Z) \Leftrightarrow$$

$$(d) \quad K(X, Y, Z, T) = -A(X)g(Y, Z) + A(Y)g(Z, X) \Leftrightarrow$$

$$(e) \quad K(X, Y, Z) = -g(Y, Z)X + g(Z, X)Y \Leftrightarrow$$

$$(f) \quad K(X, Y, Z, W) = -g(Y, Z)g(W, X) + g(Z, X)g(Y, W)$$

After some computation, we get

$$(4.3) \quad (a) \quad K(X, Y, \bar{Z}) - \overline{K(X, Y, Z)} = -F(Y, Z)\bar{X} - F(Z, X)\bar{Y} + g(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z})\bar{X} - g(\bar{Z}, \bar{X})\bar{Y} - A(X)F(Y, Z)T - A(Y)F(Z, X)T - A(Y)A(Z)\bar{X} + A(Z)A(X)\bar{Y} \Leftrightarrow$$

$$(b) \quad K(X, Y, \bar{Z}, W) - \overline{K(X, Y, Z, W)} = F(Y, Z)g(\bar{W}, \bar{X}) + F(Z, X)g(\bar{Y}, \bar{W}) + F(Y, W)g(\bar{Z}, \bar{X}) + F(W, X)g(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) - A(W)A(X)F(Y, Z) - A(Y)A(W)F(Z, X) - A(Y)A(Z)F(W, X) - A(Z)A(X)F(Y, W).$$

Also,

$$(4.4) \quad K(X, Y, \bar{Z}, \bar{W}) - \overline{K(X, Y, Z, W)} = F(Y, Z)F(W, X) - F(Z, X)F(Y, W) + g(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z})g(\bar{W}, \bar{X}) - g(\bar{Z}, \bar{X})g(\bar{Y}, \bar{W}) - A(W)A(X)g(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) - A(Y)A(Z)g(\bar{W}, \bar{X}) + A(Z)A(X)g(\bar{Y}, \bar{W}) + A(Y)A(W)g(\bar{Z}, \bar{X}).$$

And

$$(4.5) \quad K(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}, \bar{Z}, \bar{W}) - \overline{K(X, Y, Z, W)} = -g(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z})g(\bar{W}, \bar{X}) + g(\bar{Z}, \bar{X})g(\bar{Y}, \bar{W}) - F(Y, Z)F(W, X) + F(Z, X)F(Y, W)$$

Adding (4.4) and (4.5), we get

$$(4.6) \quad K(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}, \bar{Z}, \bar{W}) - \overline{K(X, Y, Z, W)} = -A(W)A(X)g(Y, Z) - A(Y)A(Z)g(W, X) + A(Z)A(X)g(Y, W) + A(Y)A(W)g(Z, X)$$

This equation is equivalent to

$$(4.7) \quad K(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) + K(X, Y, Z) - A(X)g(Y, Z)T - A(Y)A(Z)X + A(Y)g(Z, X)T + A(Z)A(X)Y = 0.$$

COMPLETELY INTEGRABLE MANIFOLDS

Barring X, Y, Z in (3.17) and using equations (3.5) (b), we see that a nearly L-Sasakian manifold is completely integrable, if

$$(5.1) \quad (B_{\bar{X}}F)(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) = (B_{\bar{Y}}F)(\bar{X}, \bar{Z}).$$

Barring X, Y, Z in (3.17) and using equations (3.10), we see that an almost L-Sasakian manifold is completely integrable, if

$$(5.2) \quad (B_{\bar{Z}}F)(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) = 0.$$

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